
LAONLP: LAO LANGUAGE NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING

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ABSTRACT

LaoNLP, the Lao language Natural Language Processing Toolkit, is an open-source tool for doing natural language processing pipelines with the Lao language in Python programming language.¹

Keywords Lao · Natural Language Processing · toolkit

1 Introduction

Natural Language Processing is a field of artificial intelligence and linguistics. Many languages research Natural Language Processing and have toolkits to help researchers or developers do natural language processing pipelines.

For the Lao language, Matthias Bethke [Matthias Bethke, 2017] released "Lingua::LO::NLP - Various Lao text processing functions". Lingua::LO::NLP can break syllables, query various syllable properties, and romanize Lao text that writes in Perl programming language, but the tool does not been maintained since 2016. Zhao Shiyu Zhao Shiyu released "SEANLP: Southeast Asia Natural Language Processing," the Southeast Asia Natural Language Processing tool that writes in Java but only supports word segmentation in the Lao language. Vee Satayamas [Vee Satayamas] released the "Chamkho" tool, which is Khmer, Lao, Myanmar, and Thai word segmentation/breaking library and command-line that writes in Rust programming language.

From previous work, there is no natural language processing toolkit for the Lao language in Python programming language, so we are developing the LaoNLP to help researchers or developers do natural language processing pipelines in the Lao language.

2 Capabilities

LaoNLP has many capabilities to help do natural language processing pipelines in the Lao language.

2.1 Word Segmentation

LaoNLP support dictionary-based word segmentation that works with the maximum matching algorithm that uses `multi_cut` from PyThaiNLP[Phatthiyaphaibun et al., 2016].

We have collect words and dictionaries for use in LaoNLP. All is an open-source dictionary license. There is the list;

- Lao-Dictionary.txt - This file comes from Brian Eugene Wilson, Robert Martin Campbell.²
- lo_spellcheck_dict.txt - This file comes from Google.³

¹LaoNLP available at <https://github.com/wannaphong/LaoNLP>.

²Lao-Dictionary.txt available at <http://code.google.com/p/lao-dictionary/>.

³lo_spellcheck_dict.txt available at https://github.com/google/language-resources/blob/master/lo/data_sets/lo_spellcheck_dict.txt.

- wiktory-20210720.txt - This file comes from Wiktionary on 20 July 2021.⁴
- lao-wannaphong.txt - This file is our work.⁵

2.2 Sentence tokenizer

LaoNLP uses the stop mark in Lao for split sentences by ".".

2.3 Part-of-speech tagging

LaoNLP support the part-of-speech tagging by Greedy Averaged Perceptron tagger [Matthew Honnibal, 2013] that the function use in PyThaiNLP. We retrained the part-of-speech tagging with SeqLabeling corpus [FoVNull] and the Yunshan Cup 2020 corpus[Fu et al., 2022].

2.4 Transliterate

LaoNLP supports the naive Lao script to Thai script transliterate and Thai script to Lao script transliterate. We use the phoneme inventories for Lao and Thai from Google for implementation.⁶

2.5 Dictionary

LaoNLP includes the dictionary for helping to do natural language processing pipelines. The list is built-in in LaoNLP other than word dictionaries for word segmentation.

- stopwords_lao.txt - Lao stop words that translated from stopwords_th.txt by @aiibe on GitHub.⁷
- lao-eng-dictionary.csv - This file is the Lao-English dictionary from the Lao Ministry of Post and Telecommunications that We download from Google.⁸

3 Conclusions and Future Work

LaoNLP is an open-source tool to help researchers or developers do natural language processing pipelines in the Lao language and support word segmentation, sentence tokenizer, part-of-speech tagging, Lao script to Thai script transliterate, Thai script to Lao script transliterate, and built-in the dictionary. We plan to implement many tasks for LaoNLP in the future, and we welcome any contributions.

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⁴wiktory-20210720.txt available at <https://github.com/wannaphong/LaoNLP/blob/master/laonlp/corpus/wiktory-20210720.txt>.

⁵wiktory-20210720.txt available at <https://github.com/wannaphong/LaoNLP/blob/master/laonlp/corpus/lao-wannaphong.txt>.

⁶The phoneme inventories for Lao and Thai from Google available at https://github.com/google/language-resources/blob/master/lo/lo_th_phonemes.txt.

⁷stopwords_th.txt available at <https://gist.github.com/aiibe/a7e279d587271e23844fba1b6239c7b3>.

⁸lao-eng-dictionary.csv available at https://github.com/google/language-resources/tree/master/third_party/lo_dictionary_by_mopt_laos.

FoVNull. FoVNull/SeqLabeling: Build a POS tagger for lao and bahasa indonesia. URL <https://github.com/FoVNull/SeqLabeling>.

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